

t-Derivations in *BF*-Algebras

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 21 December 2022 Corresponding Author: Sri Gemawati	In this paper, we define the concept of (ℓ, r) - t -derivation and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in <i>BF</i> -algebras. Then, we investigate some properties of (ℓ, r) and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in <i>BF</i> -algebras. Also, we obtain some properties of regular of t -derivation in <i>BF</i> -algebra. Finally, we investigate the properties of the concept in <i>BF</i> -algebras.
KEYWORDS: <i>BF</i> -algebra, (ℓ, r) and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation, t -derivation	

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2002, Neggers and Kim [1] introduced a new algebraic structure called *B*-algebra. *B*-algebra was defined as a nonempty set *A* with a constant 0 and a binary operation * when satisfies the axioms: (B1) $a * a = 0$, (B2) $a * 0 = a$, and (B3) $(a * b) * c = a * (c * (0 * b))$ for all $a, b, c \in A$. Walendziak [2] defined and study one of the generalizations of *B*- algebra: *BF*- algebra. It's satisfying (B. 1), (B. 2) and (BF) $0 * (a * b) = b * a$ for all $a, b \in A$.

The concept of derivative was first introduced in the study of rings and near rings [3]. However, as abstract algebras developed, the concept of derivation has been studied in other algebraic structures. Al-Shehrie [4] defined and studied the concept derivation of *B*-algebra. The result obtained is to define (ℓ, r) and (r, ℓ) -derivation, regular in *B*-algebra and obtained the properties. Some development in the concept of t -derivation is presented in the following studies [5]–[7]. In 2014, Soleimani and Jahangiri [8] introduced a new notion called t -derivation of *B*-algebra. They defined a self-map d_t in *B*-algebra $(A; *, 0)$ with $d_t(a) = a * t$ for all $a, t \in A$ then they defined the concept of (ℓ, r) and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation on *B*-algebra. Recently, the concept of t -derivation on the other type of algebras was also studied by another author, see for examples [9] and [10].

In this paper, we define the concept of (ℓ, r) and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation, also t -derivation in *BF*-algebra. Then, we investigate the properties.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Some theories about *B*-algebra, *BF*-algebra also the derivation concept of *B*-algebra and t -derivation are given in this section.

Definition 2.1. [1] *A* is a nonempty set with a constant 0 and with a binary operation * is *B*- algebra if satisfies the axioms:

- (B1) $a * a = 0$,
 - (B2) $a * 0 = a$,
 - (B3) $(a * b) * c = a * (c * (0 * b))$
- for all $a, b, c \in A$.

Lemma 2.2. [1] If $(A; *, 0)$ is *B*- algebra, then

- (i) $0 * (0 * a) = a$,
- (ii) $(a * b) * (0 * b) = a$,
- (iii) $b * c = b * (0 * (0 * c))$,
- (iv) $a * (b * c) = (a * (0 * c)) * b$,
- (v) If $a * c = b * c$, then $a = b$,
- (vi) If $a * b = 0$, then $a = b$,

For all $a, b, c \in A$.

Proof. The proof of this Lemma has been given in [1].

Example 2.1. Let $A = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

Table 2.1: Cayley's table for $(A; *, 0)$.

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	1	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	1	2	0

Then $(A; *, 0)$ is a *B*-algebra.

The concept of derivation in *B*-algebra was studied in [4]. Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a *B*-algebra, defined $a \wedge b = b * (b * a)$ for all $a, b \in A$.

Definition 2.3.[4] Let $(A; *, 0)$ is a *B*-algebra. A self-map d of A is a (ℓ, r) -derivation of A if it satisfying

$$d(a * b) = (d(a) * b) \wedge (a * d(b)),$$

for all $a, b \in A$ and is a (r, ℓ) -derivation of A if it satisfying

$$d(a * b) = (a * d(b)) \wedge (d(a) * b),$$

for all $a, b \in A$. Then d is called a derivation of A if d is a (ℓ, r) and also (r, ℓ) -derivation of A .

Definition 2.4. [4] Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a *B*-algebra. d is a self-map of A and it's said to be regular if $d(0) = 0$.

Definition 2.5.[8] Let $(A; *, 0)$ is a *B*-algebra. d_t is a self-map of A , for any $t \in A$ defined by $d_t(a) = a * t$ for all $a \in A$.

Definition 2.6.[8] Let $(A; *, 0)$ be *B*-algebra. For any $t \in A$, d_t is a self-map of A and it's called (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A if it's satisfying

$$d_t(a * b) = (d_t(a) * b) \wedge (a * d_t(b)),$$

for all $a, b \in A$ and is called (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of A if it's satisfying

$$d_t(a * b) = (a * d_t(b)) \wedge (d_t(a) * b),$$

for all $a, b \in A$. Then d_t is a t -derivation of A when d_t is a (ℓ, r) and also a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of A .

One of the other generalizations of *B*-algebra is *BG*-algebra. In the following, the definition of *BG*-algebra will be given.

Definition 2.7.[11] A *BG*-algebra is a non-empty set A with a binary operation $*$ and a constant 0 if satisfies the following axioms $(B1)$, $(B2)$ and $(BG)(a * b) * (0 * b) = a$ for all $a, b \in A$.

Definition 2.8.[2] Let A is a *BF*-algebra. For all $a, b \in A$ satisfying:

$$(B1) a * a = 0,$$

$$(B2) a * 0 = a,$$

$$(BF) 0 * (a * b) = b * a.$$

Examples 2.2. Given $A = \{0, x, y, z\}$ is a set with this following Cayley table:

Table 2.2: Cayley table for $(A; *, 0)$

*	0	x	y	z
0	0	x	y	z
x	x	0	z	y
y	y	z	0	x
z	z	y	x	0

Based on Table 2.2, it can be proved that A is *BF*-algebra.

Proposition 2.9.[2] Let $(A; *, 0)$ is a *BF*-algebra, then the following hold:

$$(i) 0 * (0 * a) = a,$$

$$(ii) \text{ If } 0 * a = 0 * b, \text{ then } a = b,$$

$$(iii) \text{ If } a * b = 0, \text{ then } b * a = 0.$$

For all $a, b \in A$.

Proof. The proof of this proposition has been proved in [2].

Definition 2.10.[2] Let A be a *BF*-algebra. Then A is *BF*₁-algebra if it's a *BG*-algebra.

Theorem 2.11.[2] Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a *BF*₁-algebra, then

$$(i) \text{ If } a * b = 0, \text{ then } a = b,$$

$$(ii) \text{ If } a * b = c * b, \text{ then } a = c,$$

$$(iii) \text{ If } b * a = b * c, \text{ then } a = c$$

For all $a, b, c \in A$.

Proof. The proof of this Theorem has been given in [2].

Theorem 2.12.[2] If $(A; *, 0)$ is a *B*-algebra, then $(A; *, 0)$ is a *BF* algebra.

Proof. This Theorem has been proven in [2].

Theorem 2.13.[2] For all $a, b, c \in A$, any *BF*-algebra which is that satisfies the identity $(a * c) * (b * c) = a * b$ is also a *B*-algebra.

Proof. This Theorem has been proven in [2].

III. MAIN RESULT

The following is given the concept of t -derivation in *BF*-algebra and investigate the properties of (ℓ, r) - t -derivation and (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in *BF*-algebra and *BF*₁-algebra.

Definition 3.1. For any $t \in A$, let d_t be a self-map of *BF*-algebra A and defined by $d_t(a) = a * t$ for all $a \in A$.

Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a *BF*-algebra. Defined $a \wedge b = b * (b * a)$ for all $a, b \in A$.

Definition 3.2. Let $(A; *, 0)$ is a *BF*-algebra, a self-map d_t of A for any $t \in A$ is called (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A , then

$$d_t(a * b) = (d_t(a) * b) \wedge (a * d_t(b))$$

for all $a, b \in A$ and is called (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of A , then

$$d_t(a * b) = (a * d_t(b)) \wedge (d_t(a) * b)$$

for all $a, b \in A$. d_t is a t -derivation of A if d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation and also a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of A .

Definition 3.3. A self-map d_t of *BF*-algebra A is regular if $d_t(0) = 0$.

The following is given a property of (ℓ, r) - t -derivation and property of (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in *BF*-algebra and some properties of *BF*₁-algebra.

Theorem 3.4. Let A is a *BF*-algebra. d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A . Let d_t regular, then we have $d_t(a) = d_t(a) \wedge a$ for all $a \in A$.

Proof. Suppose $(A; *, 0)$ is a BF -algebra and d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A . Since d_t is a regular, by (B.2) obtained

$$\begin{aligned} d_t(a) &= d_t(a * 0) \\ &= (d_t(a) * 0) \wedge (a * d_t(0)) \\ &= d_t(a) \wedge (a * 0) \\ d_t(a) &= d_t(a) \wedge a. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is proved that if d_t regular, then $d_t(a) = d_t(a) \wedge a$ for all $a \in A$.

Theorem 3.5. Let d_t is a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in BF - algebra A and d_t regular, then we define $d_t(a) = a \wedge d_t(a)$ for all $a \in A$.

Proof. Suppose d_t is a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in BF -algebra A and d_t is a regular, then by (B.2) obtained

$$\begin{aligned} d_t(a) &= d_t(a * 0) \\ &= (a * d_t(0)) \wedge (d_t(a) * 0) \\ &= (a * 0) \wedge d_t(a) \\ d_t(a) &= a \wedge d_t(a). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is proved that if d_t is regular, then $d_t(a) = a \wedge d_t(a)$ for all $a \in A$.

Lemma 3.6. Let $(A; *, 0)$ be a BF_1 -algebra, then d_t is an injective function.

Proof. Let $d_t(a) = d_t(b)$ for all $a, b \in A$, then by Theorem 2.11(ii) obtained

$$\begin{aligned} d_t(a) &= d_t(b) \\ a * t &= b * t \\ a &= b \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is proved that d_t is an injective function.

Theorem 3.7. Let $(A; *, 0)$ is a BF_1 -algebra. d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A . d_t regular if and only if d_t is an identity.

Proof. Suppose d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation in BF_1 -algebra A . Because d_t regular, then by (B1), (B2) and Theorem 2.11 (iii) obtained

$$\begin{aligned} d_t(0) &= d_t(a * a) \\ 0 &= (d_t(a) * a) \wedge (a * d_t(a)) \\ (a * d_t(a)) * (a * d_t(a)) &= (a * d_t(a)) \\ &\quad * [(a * d_t(a)) * (d_t(a) * a)] \\ (a * d_t(a)) &= (a * d_t(a)) * (d_t(a) * a) \\ (a * d_t(a)) * 0 &= (a * d_t(a)) * (d_t(a) * a) \\ &= d_t(a) * a \\ d_t(a) * d_t(a) &= d_t(a) * a \\ d_t(a) &= a. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is proved that d_t is an identity. Then, on the other side, suppose that d_t is an identity with $d_t(a) = a$ for all $a \in A$, then $d_t(0) = 0$. So, it is proved that d_t regular. This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.8. Let d_t is a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation in BF_1 -algebra A . d_t regular if and only if d_t identity.

Proof. Suppose d_t is a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of BF_1 -algebra A . Because d_t regular, then by Theorem 3.5, axioms (B.1), (B.2) and Theorem 2.11(iii) obtained

$$\begin{aligned} d_t(a) &= a \wedge d_t(a) \\ d_t(a) * 0 &= d_t(a) * (d_t(a) * a) \\ 0 &= d_t(a) * a \\ d_t(a) * d_t(a) &= d_t(a) * a \\ d_t(a) &= a. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, it is proved that d_t is an identity. Then, conversely suppose that d_t is identity with $d_t(a) = a$ for all $a \in A$, then $d_t(0) = 0$. Therefore, it is proved that d_t is regular.

Theorem 3.9. Let d_t is a t -derivation in BF_1 -algebra A . d_t regular if only if d_t is identity.

Proof. Suppose $(A; *, 0)$ be a BF_1 -algebra, by Theorem 3.7 we have that if d_t is a (ℓ, r) - t -derivation of A , then d_t regular if and only if d_t identity and from Theorem 3.8 we have that if d_t is a (r, ℓ) - t -derivation of A , so d_t is regular if and only if d_t identity. Therefore, it is proved that if d_t is a t -derivation in A , then d_t regular if and only if d_t identity.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we can conclude in general in BF -algebra, the (ℓ, r) - t -derivation's properties are different from (r, ℓ) - t -derivation's properties. However, in BF_1 -algebra they have the properties that prevail in (ℓ, r) and also in (r, ℓ) - t -derivation: if and only if d_t regular then d_t identity. Therefore, if d_t is a t -derivation in A , then d_t regular if and only if d_t identity in BF_1 -algebra.

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